

Review Article

A review of phase change materials: Selection, degradation, and materials compatibility

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ABSTRACT

As concerns about climate change and excess energy requirements intensify, thermal energy storage (TES) systems have emerged as a promising solution by enabling the storage of excess heat. One of the technologies uses phase change materials (PCMs), which have appeared as an alternative to enhance the performance of renewables (i.e., solar, geothermal) by acting as thermal storage batteries. This paper presents a comprehensive review of latent heat TES systems, emphasising the critical criteria for selecting PCMs used in these applications. Additionally, the categories of the available PCMs are presented. This review also discusses their thermal stability over time, as PCMs can experience performance degradation due to repeated heating and cooling cycles or prolonged exposure to high temperatures. Furthermore, the paper highlights the importance of compatibility between PCMs and structural materials, summarising the interaction of various metals and alloys, and polymers in contact with different PCMs. Compatibility could ensure the long-term operational reliability of TES systems. The paper further presents the challenges and considerations for the large-scale deployment of PCM-based TES systems.

1. Thermal energy storage

Due to rising climate concerns and increasing energy demand, substantial efforts have been made by researchers, industry stakeholders, and policymakers to promote sustainable renewable energy systems [1–4]. A key enabler of this transition is the ability to store energy efficiently and dispatch it when required, thereby mitigating the intermittency of renewable energy sources. Thermal energy storage (TES) systems have emerged as a crucial component of this strategy [5,6]. TES utilises the change in the internal energy of a material, in the form of either sensible heat, latent heat, or thermochemical heat [7–10].

The value of TES lies in its ability to store surplus thermal energy during periods of low demand or high renewable energy generation, and subsequently discharge it when demand peaks. In this way, TES systems effectively function as thermal batteries [11], enabling load balancing and enhancing flexibility in energy distribution. TES contributes towards reduced energy costs, improved overall system efficiency, and greater sustainability. Moreover, by offsetting the reliance on fossil fuel-based power generation during peak periods, TES plays a critical role in

lowering greenhouse gas emissions and fostering a more environmentally responsible energy infrastructure [12].

The TES market has recently experienced rapid growth, driven by increasing electricity demand during peak periods, the expanding deployment of concentrated solar power plants, and the rising need for efficient heating and cooling solutions in smart buildings and infrastructure [13]. The global TES market is projected to reach approximately USD 16.05 billion by 2034, growing at a compound annual growth rate of 9.5% from 2023 to 2034, as illustrated in Fig. 1 [13].

Despite this promising outlook, TES technologies still face notable scientific and engineering challenges. These include the development of effective control mechanisms, enhancement of material durability and thermal stability, and improvements in system reliability [14]. These challenges can be broadly categorised into three areas: TES material challenges, TES component/device-level challenges, and TES system-level challenges [15].

This review focuses specifically on the first category – TES materials – highlighting recent advancements aimed at achieving high energy density (through integration with compatible phase change materials, or

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PCMs), enhanced durability and lifespan (by minimising thermal and chemical degradation), wide operational temperature ranges (for efficient performance at both low and high temperatures), improved thermal conductivity and energy transfer efficiency, and cost-effectiveness.

1.1. Types of thermal energy storage

TES systems operate by storing energy between two temperature levels, which are defined by the specific requirements of the application. The process of introducing energy into the system is referred to as charging, whilst the extraction of stored energy is known as discharging [16]. The input energy for charging can be sourced from various renewable and natural resources, including geothermal and solar energy [17,18]. TES systems are generally categorised into three main types, based on the underlying heat storage mechanism: Sensible Heat Storage (SHS), Latent Heat Storage (LHS), and Thermochemical Heat Storage (THS). These classifications are illustrated in Fig. 2 (adapted from [19]).

In SHS systems [20,21], the material is heated to a higher/final temperature (T_f , in K) to store the heat (Q , in kJ), utilising the specific heat capacity ($C_p(T)$, in kJ/kgK) of the material – which can vary as a function of temperature. The amount of heat that can be stored through SHS is defined by the relation given in Eq. (1).

$$Q = \int_{T_i}^{T_f} mC_p(T)dT \tag{1}$$

Here T_i (in K) means the initial temperature of the material, m (kg) refers to the mass or the amount of the storage material, and dT stands for the temperature change. Table 1 lists various materials and their properties, taken from the reference [22], that are used for SHS.

In LHS systems, the enthalpy or latent heat of phase change (ΔH_f , kJ/kg) of a PCM is utilised when phase changes happen in the PCM. The total storage capacity of the LHS system using a PCM can be determined using the equation provided in Eq. (2).

$$Q = \int_{T_i}^{T_s} mC_{psolid}dT + \int_{T_s}^{T_l} m \frac{dH_f}{dT} dT + \int_{T_l}^{T_f} mC_{pliquid}dT \tag{2}$$

Here T_s (in K) and T_l (in K) mean the solidus and the liquidus

Fig. 2. Types of thermal energy storage systems [18].

temperature of the material, respectively. C_{psolid} and $C_{pliquid}$ are the specific heat capacities (in kJ/kgK) in the solid and the liquid form of the material, respectively.

In THS systems [26,27], heat is stored through a reversible thermochemical process, utilising the heat absorbed and released during the formation and breaking of molecular bonds for energy storage. THS technologies are still at an early stage of development and require further work to understand reaction kinetics, reversibility, reactor design, and cost, which currently limit their widespread deployment.

1.2. Importance of latent heat storage

The temperature difference (ΔT) between charging and discharging phases is a critical parameter in the selection of an efficient TES system. A larger ΔT enables SHS systems to achieve higher energy storage density. However, when ΔT is relatively low, LHS systems – typically using PCMs – are often preferred due to their ability to store substantial energy within a narrow temperature range. Additionally, among the three TES types, LHS systems have garnered significant attention for their superior energy storage efficiency [5,28]. In low-temperature-gradient applications, LHS systems can store more energy in a

Fig. 1. The thermal energy storage market size from 2023 to 2034 [13].

Table 1

Some materials and their properties for sensible heat storage systems [22–25]. All materials are in the solid state, except water, which is in the liquid state. Consequently, the melting temperatures of the solid samples occur in the higher temperature range, whereas the phase transition temperature of water occurs in the lower temperature range.

Material	Density (kg/m ³)	Specific heat (kJ/kgK)	Heat capacity (kJ/m ³ K)	Melting temperature (°C)	Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	Thermal diffusivity ($\times 10^6$ m ² /s)
Aluminium	2707	0.896	2425	660	204	84.1
Cast iron	7900	0.837	6612	1150	29.3	4.431
Granite	2640	0.82	2164	1215	1.7–4.0	0.799–1.840
Sand	1555	0.8	1244	1500	0.15–0.25	1.172
Concrete	2240	0.75	1680–1800	1000	1.7	0.356–0.514
Brick	1698	0.84	1426	1800	1.04	0.484
Rock	2480	0.84	2086.6	1800	2–7	1.45
Water	1000	4.184	4184	0	0.6	0.14–0.17

compact volume compared to SHS, thus reducing the required storage tank size. This makes LHS particularly suitable for space-constrained environments. Additionally, many PCMs exhibit minimal volumetric change during phase transitions, simplifying system design and reducing maintenance requirements. Nevertheless, certain PCMs may expand by 20% or more during phase change, necessitating careful engineering controls to accommodate this variation [29]. In contrast, THS can achieve very high heat storage densities and allows for long-term storage and transport under ambient conditions. However, THS systems are generally more complex, requiring precise control over reaction processes. This added complexity can limit the practicality of THS for many applications, making LHS an attractive alternative that balances high storage density, ease of use, and operational safety effectively [30]. Table 2 compares different aspects of the TES systems, adapted from references [30, 31].

In the LHS system, PCMs play a crucial role [32], with phase changes occurring in various forms: solid–solid, solid–liquid, solid–gas, liquid–gas, and their reverse processes [33–36], as showcased in Fig. 3.

In solid–solid transformations, the heat released and volume changes are smaller compared to solid–liquid transformations. However, PCMs involving solid–solid offer advantages in container design and reduce leakage risks [37]. On the other hand, solid–liquid and solid–gas transformations provide higher heat release but present challenges with containment due to significant volume changes [5,7]. Although the solid–liquid transformation releases less latent heat than the solid–gas change, the relatively small volume change (about 10%) [5] makes it less complex and more economically viable. The limitations of current technologies often result in unstable behaviour and excessive pressure during solid–gas and liquid–gas phase transitions [38]; hence, this review focuses on solid–liquid transformation-based LHS systems. Developing an effective LHS system requires a thorough understanding of the properties of the PCM used and its long-term stability. Additionally, the construction material for the LHS system must be compatible with the PCM, particularly in terms of corrosion resistance, requiring mitigation and control strategies. The following sections delve into these critical aspects of LHS systems.

2. Phase change materials

A PCM, as mentioned above, serves as the latent heat storage medium [39]. The working principle of a PCM during solid–liquid transformation is illustrated in Fig. 4, redrawn from reference [40]. The increase in temperature allows the PCM to change its state from solid to

Fig. 3. Phase changes that can occur in PCMs.

liquid phase, and hence, absorbing the heat. The drop in the temperature returns the PCM to its solid form and releases the energy.

The melting temperature of the material is a very important property, as it defines the temperature at which energy is stored in the LHS [41]. Depending on the application and the use case, other desirable characteristics that should be carefully considered when selecting an appropriate PCM for TES systems include thermal, physical, kinetic, and chemical properties, as well as their cost [16,42].

2.1. Properties of a desired phase change material

The PCM should match the desired operating temperature for heating and cooling, with a high latent heat for optimal performance. However, volumetric changes and vapour pressure should be minimal to avoid containment issues. Higher thermal conductivity is important for efficient heat transfer during charging and discharging. Supercooling is a critical concern [43], as 5–10 °C of supercooling can completely

Table 2

Comparison of different heat storage systems, adapted from references [30, 31].

Type	Capacity (kWh/t)	Power (MW)	Maturity	Storage time	Technical difficulty
THS (chemical reactions)	120–250	0.01–1	Laboratory	Short- to long-term	Difficult
LHS (PCM)	50–150	0.001–1	Pilot plant	Short-term	Moderate
SHS (hot water)	10–50	0.001–10	Commercialisation	Long-term	Easy

Fig. 4. Working principle of a PCM [34].

Fig. 5. PCM types classified by temperature.

inhibit heat extraction [5]. Since PCMs can degrade over time [44], chemical/thermal stability is crucial. Additionally, the PCM should be non-toxic, non-flammable, and non-explosive for safety reasons. Further sustainability considerations include the PCM being abundant, available, and cost-effective. Table 3 summarises the key factors to consider when searching for a suitable PCM [5].

Beyond these classical criteria, PCM selection must also consider thermal hysteresis, which can reduce energy recovery and impair system efficiency, and phase transition sharpness, since many organic and eutectic PCMs transition over a temperature range rather than at a single point, affecting thermal responsiveness [45–47]. Volumetric energy density is often more practical than gravimetric latent heat, as it influences tank size and system footprint [48]. Low thermal conductivity can limit charge/discharge rates, causing incomplete phase change and thermal stratification [49].

2.2. Classification of phase change materials

Various PCMs with distinct characteristics are available for TES applications. The PCMs can be classified into several categories, based on melting temperature, as presented in Fig. 5 [50,51], and based on their composition (organic, inorganic, and eutectic PCMs [52]), as shown in Fig. 6. No single PCM can provide all the properties needed for an ideal TES. Therefore, a carefully designed system is essential to achieve the desired TES system.

2.2.1. Organic PCMs

The most commonly used organic PCMs in storage applications are pure n-alkanes, esters, and fatty acids. Organic PCMs provide high heat capacity and a suitable range of phase change temperatures. They are generally non-corrosive and exhibit minimal or no supercooling [53].

Table 3

The key factors to consider when searching for a suitable PCM [5].

Thermal properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Suitable phase-transformation temperature ii. High latent heat of transformation iii. High thermal conductivity
Physical properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Favourable phase equilibrium ii. High density iii. Small volume change during phase change iv. Low vapour pressure
Kinetic properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. No supercooling ii. Sufficient crystallisation rate
Chemical properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Long-term chemical stability ii. Compatibility with materials of construction iii. No toxicity iv. No fire hazard
Economics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Abundant ii. Available iii. Cost-effective

Fig. 6. PCM types classified by composition [52].

These organic PCMs can be further classified into paraffins and non-paraffins.

2.2.1.1. Paraffins. Paraffin waxes are primarily a mixture of straight-chain n-alkanes with the chemical structure $\text{CH}_3-(\text{CH}_2)_n-\text{CH}_3$ [53], or can be seen as the type of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_{2n+2}$ saturated hydrocarbons [54]. For values of $n < 5$, paraffins are gaseous, for $n = 5$ (pentane, C_5H_{12}) to $n = 15$ (pentadecane, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{32}$), the paraffins are liquid at ambient temperatures and pressures, and for $n > 15$, they appear from viscous liquids to solid waxes [55]. A significant amount of heat is released during the crystallisation of the (CH_3) groups, and as the length of the alkane chain increases, both the melting point and the latent heat of fusion also increase [5]. Additionally, crystallisation is quicker for paraffin compared to salt hydrates and exhibits little or no supercooling, with a volume change of 10% observed with the transition [54]. The thermal conductivity of paraffin is generally low, which is a limiting factor for its use [52]. Table 4 lists various paraffin waxes along with their thermal properties, as sourced from the referenced studies [53,56–63].

2.2.1.2. Non-paraffins. These PCMs exhibit highly diverse properties, meaning each PCM possesses distinct characteristics, unlike paraffins, which tend to have similar properties. They can be classified into fatty acids and other non-paraffin organic substances, such as other acids, esters, fatty alcohols, and glycols [5]. Some of the non-paraffins and non-fatty acids, along with their thermophysical properties, are presented in Table 5, taken from reference [5].

Most of these non-paraffins are more flammable compared to paraffins and should not be exposed to extremely high temperatures or oxidising agents. Their key characteristics include a high heat of fusion, low thermal conductivity, generally low flash points, varying degrees of toxicity, and instability at elevated temperatures. However, there are exceptions, such as sebacic acid, with a flash point of 220 °C, which is considered a high value.

Table 4

Thermal properties of paraffin waxes [53,56–63]. It should be noted that the melting and crystallisation temperatures of PCMs may differ due to supercooling and hysteresis effects associated with nucleation and crystallisation kinetics, resulting in a temperature gap between heating and cooling cycles.

Paraffin wax	Molecular formula	Molar mass (g mol ⁻¹)	Melting temperature (°C)	Crystallisation temperature (°C)	Latent heat (kJ/kg)
n-Dodecane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₀ CH ₃	170.3	-10	-16	216
n-Tridecane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₁ CH ₃	184.4	-5	-9	160
n-Tetradecane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₂ CH ₃	198	5-6	0	227
n-Pentadecane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₃ CH ₃	212	10	5	205
n-Hexadecane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₄ CH ₃	226	18-19	17	237
n-Heptadecane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₅ CH ₃	240	22	22	171
n-Octadecane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₆ CH ₃	254	28	25	242
n-Nonadecane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₇ CH ₃	268	32-33	27	222
n-Eicosane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₈ CH ₃	282	36-37	31	247
n-Heneicosane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₉ CH ₃	296	39-41	32	201
n-Docosane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂₀ CH ₃	310	42-45	43	157
n-Tricosane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂₁ CH ₃	324	48.9	51	142
n-Tetracosane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂₂ CH ₃	338	50-51	48-49	160
n-Pentacosane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂₃ CH ₃	352	54	47	164
n-Hexacosane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂₄ CH ₃	366	56	53-54	255
n-Heptacosane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂₅ CH ₃	380	59	53	159
n-Octacosane	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂₆ CH ₃	394	61	54	202

Fatty acids, in particular, have a higher heat of fusion compared to paraffins. Additionally, they show consistent melting and freezing behaviour, without supercooling during freezing [64,65]. The general formula for fatty acids is CH₃(CH₂)_{2n}COOH. However, a downside of fatty acids is that they generally have a high cost, although the final price usually varies depending on the exact type and market fluctuations. Moreover, fatty acids exhibit mild corrosive properties [5]. Some examples of fatty acids are presented in Table 6, taken from references [53, 66–70]. The most used fatty acids for building applications and solar thermal applications are lauric (LA), stearic (SA), myristic (MA), palmitic (PA) and capric acid (CA). They can be used in mixtures, but suffer from low conductivity [54]. Esters are known for their relatively low melting points, making them useful for applications needing moderate temperature regulation. Fatty alcohols also provide high latent heat and are often used in encapsulated forms for building materials. Glycols, particularly polyethylene glycol (PEG), an important semi-crystalline polymer, are flexible in design due to their variable molecular weight, allowing a range of melting points for different temperature control needs [71–73]. PEG general formula consists of repeating dimethyl ether chains with hydroxyl-terminated groups, OH–CH₂–(–CH₂–O–CH₂)_n–CH₂–OH, and possesses the dual feature of water solubility and organic solubility. Its melting point varies from 4 to 70 °C, and has a large heat of fusion (117–170 kJ/kg), attributed to a high degree of crystallinity. PEG is considered to be suitable for solar TESs alone or in blends [54].

2.2.2. Inorganic PCMs

Inorganic PCMs can be categorised into various inorganic substances, salts (nitrates, nitrites, hydroxides, chlorides, sulphates, carbonates, fluorides) [75] and their hydrated form, eutectics, alloys, and mixtures [54]; metals [76]. These materials are known for their high thermal conductivity, greater energy storage capacity, and relatively low cost compared to organic PCMs. Although inorganic PCMs have a great potential in the TES field, some drawbacks include corrosion, phase separation [77], and their maintenance presents a significant challenge [78].

Metallic PCMs tend to maintain relatively consistent heats of fusion over multiple melting and freezing cycles [5,78,79] – this is not the case for most salt hydrate PCMs, as phase separation appears. Due to gravity, some anhydrous salts accumulate at the bottom of the container, resulting in a continuous degradation of their storage capacity and deterioration of service life [80]. More details are provided in the subsections below.

2.2.2.1. Salt hydrates.

Salt hydrates are combinations of inorganic salts

and water, forming crystalline structures with the formula AB.nH₂O. Some of the salt hydrates, taken from references [80, 81], are mentioned in Table 7. The phase change from solid to liquid in these materials involves either dehydration or rehydration of the salt, a process thermodynamically similar to melting or freezing. When heated, salt hydrates may melt into a form with fewer water molecules (AB.mH₂O, as shown in Eq. (3)) or anhydrous salt (AB, as shown in Eq. (4)), along with the release of water.

A key issue with salt hydrates is incongruent melting, where the released water is insufficient to dissolve all the solid salt, causing the denser solid to sink to the bottom of the container and become inaccessible for recombination with water during freezing, as illustrated in Fig. 7, adapted from [71]. This results in a gradual decline in performance over multiple cycles.

Container leakages and damages attributed to corrosion are frequently a challenging part of salt hydrates for heat storage. It is well known that metal containers are selected for improved heat exchange and metal fins for boosted thermal conductivity. However, due to early corrosion occurrence, salt hydrates are proven to be less preferred [84]. Another challenge is supercooling, due to their poor nucleation properties, which delays crystallisation. This issue can be addressed by adding nucleating agents or retaining some crystals in a cooler region to trigger nucleation. The spontaneous formation of lower hydrates (hydrates after losing water content) can also be mitigated by adding chemicals to increase the solubility of the lower hydrates. Incongruent melting can be managed through methods like mechanical stirring, encapsulating the PCM, adding thickening agents to suspend solids, using excess water to prevent supersaturation, or modifying the chemical composition to achieve congruent behaviour [5,85,86]. Another issue is the temperature control of salt hydrates, which is crucial for making them work effectively across different types of energy storage systems [84]. The aforementioned three challenges are illustrated in Fig. 8.

Despite these challenges, salt hydrates are favoured for latent heat thermal storage systems because of their high latent heat per unit volume, relatively good thermal conductivity, and small volume changes during phase transitions. They are plastic-compatible and cost-effective [85]. Salt hydrates display three distinct melting behaviours: 1) Congruent melting: The anhydrous salt fully dissolves in its water of hydration. 2) Incongruent melting: The salt is not completely soluble, leading to phase separation. 3) Semi-congruent melting: The solid and liquid phases have different compositions during the transition [5].

Table 5
Non-paraffins, alongside their thermal properties, taken from reference [5].

PCM category	Material	Melting temperature (°C)	Latent heat (kJ/kg)
Fatty acids	Formic acid	7.8	247
	D-Lactic acid	26	184
	Glutaric acid	97.5	156
	Glycolic acid	63	109
	Acrylic acid	68	115
Esters	Methyl palmitate	29	205
	Methyl eicosanate	45	230
	Methyl behenate	52	234
	Trimyristin	33–57	201–213
	Methyl brombrenzoate	81	126
Ketones	Camphenilone	39	205
	Caprylone	40	259
	Heptadecanone	41	201
	2-Heptadecanone	48	218
	3-Heptadecanone	48	218
	4-Heptadecanone	41	197
	9-Heptadecanone	51	213
	Bromcamphor	77	174
	Alcohols	Cetyl alcohol	49.3
Glycerin		17.9	198.7
Aromatics compounds	Thymol	51.5	115
	Alpha naphthol	96	163
	Phenol	41	120
	Durene	79.3	156
	Stibene	124	167
	Dinto toluent (2,4)	70	111
	Benzoic acid	121.7	142.8
	Phenylacetic acid	76.7	102
	Hydrocinnamic acid	48	118
	Quinone	115	171
	Catechol	104.3	207
	O-Nitroaniline	50	93
	p-Bromophenol	63.5	86
	Nitro naphthalene	56.7	103
Paraffins/waxes	Docasyl bromide	40	201
	1-Cyclohexyloctadecane	41	218
Amines & amides	Bee wax	61.8	177
	p-Joluidine	43.3	167
	α-Nephthylamine	50	93
	Diphenyl amine	52.9	107
	Benzylamine	78	174
	Acetanilide	118.9	222
	Benzamide	127.2	169.4
	Cyanamide	44	209
	Thiosinamine	77	140
Halogenated organics	p-Dichlorobenzene	53.1	121
	O-Xylene dichloride	55	121
	p-Xylene dichloride	100	138.7
	α-Chloroacetic acid	61.2	130
	β-Chloroacetic acid	56	147
	Chloroacetic acid	56	130
Others	Camphene	50	238
	Oxolate	54.3	178
	Hypophosphoric acid	55	213

2.2.2.2. Metallics. These PCMs consist of low-melting metals and metal eutectics [87,88], which have seen limited use in PCM applications due to concerns about their weight [5] and suitability for building applications, due to variability in their melting and solidification temperatures [54]. However, they provide high melting enthalpy per unit volume and excellent thermal conductivity [89]. Table 8, adapted from reference [89], lists some of the selected metallics. Their key features include: (i) low heat of fusion per unit weight, (ii) high heat of fusion per unit volume, (iii) superior thermal conductivity, (iv) low specific heat, and (v) relatively low vapour pressure.

2.2.3. Eutectic

Eutectic materials are a minimum-melting composition of two or more components with congruent melting and freezing points [90].

They melt and freeze without segregation. This property makes them promising PCMs due to their consistent phase transitions. For a given material system, the melting behaviour can be tuned by varying the weight percentage of each component. However, the true eutectic composition has a fixed ratio and exhibits a single melting temperature; deviations from this composition may shift the phase-change temperature but generally result in a broader melting range [5]. Eutectics typically exhibit high thermal conductivity and density, but they have relatively low latent and specific heat capacities [91]. However, there are exceptions with some eutectics having high latent heat, such as the ones mentioned here [92,93]. Despite their advantages, eutectics are less commonly used compared to other types of PCMs. They are made up of organic-organic, organic-inorganic and inorganic-inorganic mixtures [94]. Table 9, adapted from reference [95], presents some eutectic PCMs.

2.3. Advantages and disadvantages of different PCM categories

Each PCM category (organic, inorganic and eutectic) might have its own advantages and disadvantages. A summary of their advantages and disadvantages is presented in Table 10, and is adapted from [96].

To provide a concise overview of the relative performance of major PCM categories across key application domains, a comparative summary of the most widely used PCMs is presented in Table 11. This table highlights their typical operating temperature ranges, latent heat capacity, thermal conductivity, chemical stability, corrosion behaviour, cost considerations, and representative applications. Such a comparison serves as a practical guideline for PCM selection tailored to specific thermal energy storage requirements.

3. Ageing of PCMs

The selection of PCMs plays a crucial role in determining the long-term efficiency of TES systems. Ensuring the stability of PCMs, especially their composition, latent heat and melting points, over repeated charge/discharge cycles is essential for maintaining (optimal) system performance. Over time, the ageing of PCMs can lead to significant performance degradation [97]. Firman et al. [98] observed that thermal ageing of beeswax reduced the discharge rate by 23.2%, resulting in over 50% decrease in power output and storage efficiency. In contrast, paraffin wax showed lower degradation, with a 14.7% reduction in discharge rate and an 18.7% decrease in power output, whilst maintaining a higher efficiency of 67.2% compared to 41.1% for beeswax. These results highlight the importance of careful PCM selection to optimise prolonged/lasting/extended storage capacity, efficiency and safety [99]. In the next sections, different aspects/issues with the ageing of PCMs are presented.

3.1. PCM degradation in TES

The degradation of PCMs in TES systems arises from several mechanisms. One prominent issue is the evaporation due to high vapour pressure; particularly in organic PCMs, high vapour pressures at elevated temperatures can result in material loss, ultimately destabilising the PCM composition. Katish et al. [100] investigated the thermal stability of several PCMs, including hexadecane, heptadecane, octadecane, RT18, RT22, and RT25. Their study found that at 30 °C, none of the PCMs exhibited measurable mass loss, highlighting their stability at lower temperatures and suitability for such conditions. However, as temperatures exceeded 150 °C, gradual mass loss began, ranging from 15% to 20%, likely due to thermal degradation and volatilisation effects. At 175 °C, the majority of these PCMs retained a large proportion of their initial mass even after enduring 10,000 thermal cycles, suggesting strong thermal resilience under repeated heating and cooling. However, between 250 °C and 350 °C, mass retention declined sharply, with nearly complete mass loss observed around 300 °C. Bayón et al. [101]

Table 6
Solid–liquid phase change thermal properties of the fatty acids [53,66–70,74].

Molecular formula	IUPAC name	Common name	Melting temperature (°C)	Latent heat (kJ/kg)
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂ COOH	n-Butanoic acid	Butyric acid	-5.6	126
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₄ COOH	n-Hexanoic acid	Caproic acid	-3	131
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₆ COOH	n-Octanoic acid	Caprylic acid	16–17	148–149
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₈ COOH	n-Decanoic acid	Capric acid	30–32	153–163
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₀ COOH	n-Dodecanoic acid	Lauric acid	41–44	178–183
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₁ COOH	n-Tridecanoic acid	Tridecylic acid	41.4	154
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₂ COOH	n-Tetradecanoic acid	Myristic acid	49–58	167–205
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₃ COOH	n-Pentadecanoic acid	Pentadecanoic acid	52–53	178
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₅ COOH	n-Heptadecanoic acid	Margaric acid	60	172.2
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₆ COOH	n-Hexadecanoic acid	Palmitic acid	61–64	186–212
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₈ COOH	n-Octadecanoic acid	Stearic acid	65–70	196–253
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₇ COOH	n-Nonadecanoic acid	Nonadecylic acid	67	192
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₉ COOH	n-Heneicosanoic acid	Heneicosylic acid	73–74	193
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₈ COOH	n-Eicosanoic acid	Arachidic acid	73 - 80	257.4
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂₁ COOH	n-Tricosanoic acid	Tricosylic acid	79	212

Table 7
Thermal phase change properties of several commonly used inorganic salt hydrate PCMs (Note: NA indicates data were not available) [80–82].

Material	Melting temperature (°C)	Latent heat (kJ/kg)	Density (kg/m ³)		Specific heat (kJ/kgK)		Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	
			Solid	Liquid	Solid	Liquid	Solid	Liquid
CaCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	29.3	171.190	1710	1562	NA	NA	1.088	0.54
Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ ·5H ₂ O	48-55	187.209	1750	1670	NA	NA	NA	NA
CH ₃ COONa·3H ₂ O	58	226.264	1450	1280	NA	NA	NA	NA
MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	117	165.169	1570	1450	2.25	2.61	0.704	0.57

Fig. 7. The representation of phase separation of salt hydrates, inspired by the reference [83].

observed that approximately 80% of the initial mass of D-mannitol was lost when it was melted at 180 °C in the air over a period of up to 16 days. This demonstrates the necessity of selecting PCMs that match the intended temperature range for each application.

Thermal degradation is another critical aspect/challenge/limitation/mechanism, particularly in high-temperature applications. PCMs subjected to high thermal cycling are prone to decomposition, forming new chemical species that can compromise thermal stability and storage efficiency over time. For example, D-mannitol, when melted at 180 °C in air, began transforming after seven days into a dark-brown, sticky paste through caramelisation processes similar to those in sugars, which failed to solidify upon cooling [101]. Analysis revealed the formation of three distinct products from this brown polymeric material, likely containing carbonyl groups, enolic groups, or α , β -unsaturated carbonyl groups. To mitigate thermal degradation, ageing experiments on D-mannitol were also conducted under inert atmospheres, such as argon (Ar) [101] and

nitrogen (N₂) [102]. However, strong browning was observed after 16 days, accompanied by a change in appearance to a soft, sticky paste and a reduction in initial mass, suggesting that the inert atmosphere did not show any improvement. A binary mixture of caprylic acid and cetyl alcohol with a eutectic composition at an 85:15 molar ratio demonstrated no changes in chemical structure after undergoing 200 melting/freezing cycles [103]. This stability was attributed to the significant difference between its melting and decomposition temperatures. Similarly, the erythritol-vermiculite form-stable PCM remained steady even after 300 melting/freezing cycles [104]. This demonstrates that it is important to understand the operating temperature window of the PCMs to be used. If stability is not maintained, PCMs should not be used in TES applications.

It is important to note that the reported ageing/thermal-stability results for the same PCM can differ across studies, and the discrepancies are often explainable once the test family and boundary

Fig. 8. Challenges in salt hydrate PCMs affecting their performance, inspired by reference [84].

Table 8

Melting temperature and latent heat of fusion for selected metallics (Note: NA indicates data were not available) [89].

Material	Melting temperature (°C)	Latent heat (kJ/kg)
Gallium	30	80.3
Cerrow eutectic	58	90.9
Bi–Cd–In eutectic	61	25
Bi–Pb–In eutectic	70	29
Bi–In eutectic	72	25
Cerrobend eutectic	70	32.6
Bi–Pb–Sn eutectic	96	NA

Table 9

List of eutectic PCMs taken from reference [95].

Mixtures	Melting temperature (°C)	Latent heat (kJ/kg)
58.3% $Mg(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ + 41.7% $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	58	106
Lauric-capric acid	18	120
61.5% $Mg(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ + 38.5% NH_4NO_3	51	131.3
49.3% $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ + 50.7% $Mg(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	58	132.3
$CaCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ + $CaBr_2 \cdot H_2O$	14	140
Lauric-palmitic acid	33	145
Na_2SO_4 (32.5%) H_2O (41.4%), $NaCl$ (6.66%), NH_4Cl (6.16%)	13	146
Lauric-stearic acid	34	150
$Mg(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$	89.90	149.163
Palmitic-stearic acid	51	160

conditions are made explicit. Broadly, two experimental families are used: (i) cycling tests (repeated melt-freeze) and (ii) thermal ageing tests (PCM maintained molten or superheated for extended durations). These test families may activate different dominant degradation drivers (e.g.,

oxidation, dehydration/volatilisation, or polymorphic/structural effects), so direct comparison without harmonised protocols can be misleading.

For example, in the case of erythritol, contrasting conclusions reported in the literature are consistent with strong sensitivities to oxygen exposure, degree/duration of superheat, and (in cycling) cooling-rate-driven polymorphism. In a study by Wusiman et al. [105], erythritol showed essentially unchanged melting enthalpy (within measurement uncertainty) after 48 h of ageing at 125–145 °C in an N_2 atmosphere, whilst the same temperature/duration in air produced markedly larger enthalpy losses, highlighting oxidation as a key contributor when oxygen is present. In oxygen-free conditions, temperature and duration still matter: increasing the holding temperature to 170–210 °C caused progressively larger enthalpy decay over 60 h [105]. The same work also demonstrated that cycling outcomes can depend on cooling rates: at ~ 3.1 °C/min, enthalpy changed little with cycling, whereas at 10 °C/min enthalpy dropped significantly, attributed to enhanced polymorphic transitions. These findings provide a mechanistic basis for why “cycling stability” and “thermal endurance” assessments can disagree if the atmosphere, superheat, and cooling rate differ between studies.

Additionally, in DSC cycling tests on D-mannitol up to 200 °C, short tests in oxygen showed clear degradation (e.g., $\sim 11.9\%$ enthalpy decrease after 20 cycles), whilst nominally oxygen-free cycling reduced this effect ($\sim 1\%$ change after 20 cycles), indicating oxidation accelerates ageing. However, even in inert/vacuum conditions, substantial degradation was observed when the PCM spent longer above its melting temperature: $\sim 9\%$ enthalpy loss after 500 cycles in inert atmosphere was reported, with the authors arguing that some degradation steps may occur even without oxygen (e.g., dehydration pathways), whilst oxygen introduces additional oxidation products and may further accelerate degradation. This clarifies why different cycling protocols (ramp rates, dwell times, sealing, purge strategy) can produce apparently contradictory outcomes even for the same nominal maximum temperature [106]. A further illustration is that stabilisation strategies can change

Table 10
Advantages and disadvantages of different PCM categories [84].

Advantages	Disadvantages
Organic	
No supercooling while undergoing phase change	Poor thermal conductivity (paraffin wax: 0.2 W/mK, pentadecane: 0.14 W/mK, 1-tetradecanol: only 0.32 W/mK)
Homogeneous and continuous phase change, meaning no phase segregation	High cost
High compatibility with encapsulation materials	High flammability, especially for non-paraffin PCMs
Congruent melting	High volatility
Corrosion resistance	Low phase change enthalpy (most below 400 kJ/kg)
Most have no toxicity	Paraffins are less compatible with plastic containers
Small volume change	Should not be exposed to oxidising agents (especially for non-paraffin PCMs)
Good chemical stability	Not eco-friendly (due to PEG and paraffin)
Adjustable and gradually increasing melting point	
Low vapour pressure while undergoing phase change	
Good reliability after thermal cycling	
Excellent freezing and melting behaviour	
Self-nucleation	
Fast nucleation rate	
Recyclable	
Long freeze-melting cycle	
Inorganic	
Large phase change enthalpy	Problematic supercooling
Superior thermal conductivity (usually more than 1 W/mK, up to ~400 for Cu)	Corrosion
Cheap (metallics excluded)	Phase segregation
Low flammability	Low thermal stability
Sharp phase change	Slight toxicity
High latent heat of fusion per unit volume	Low reliability, dehydration, after thermal cycling
Recyclable	Decomposition
Small volume changes on melting	Less compatible with encapsulation materials compared with organic PCMs
Compatible with plastic	Incongruent melting
	Poor nucleating behaviour
	Too heavy for metallic PCMs
Eutectic	
Sharp melting temperature	Supercooling exists
No phase segregation	Unpleasant and strong odours
High volumetric thermal storage density	Insufficient combinations have been studied
Adjustable melting point and latent heat due to different kinds and dosage combinations	High cost

the dominant ageing mechanisms: in a shape-stable composite (α -mannitol impregnated in calcined expanded vermiculite), only modest enthalpy losses (~4.8% in melting enthalpy) were observed after 100 heating/cooling cycles, with XRD/FTIR peak positions largely unchanged [107]. This result is not directly comparable to pure-PCM cycling because confinement/support interactions can suppress leakage and potentially limit oxygen transport and/or change crystallisation behaviour.

Moreover, in the case of fatty acids, palmitic acid (PA) shows a clear example of conflicting magnitudes of reported degradation. In an accelerated cycling study of up to 10,000 cycles, PA exhibited only a small latent heat reduction (~3.05% after 10,000 cycles) and no detectable chemical-structure change by FTIR, suggesting high chemical stability and attributing property drift mainly to impurities/nucleation effects [108]. In contrast, another study reported much larger reductions in PA's latent heat after 1000-1500 cycles (e.g., melting enthalpy decreasing from ~181 kJ/kg initially to ~146-149 kJ/kg after cycling), despite only small shifts in melting/freezing temperatures (~2 °C) [109]. These differences are plausibly explained by non-standardised cycling protocols and measurement contexts, including: temperature ranges and dwell times, sealing and gas environment (oxidative vs inert), sample containment material and headspace, and DSC evaluation

choices (baseline selection and sampling strategy).

Overall, the above comparisons support the conclusion that discrepancies across ageing studies often reflect different degradation drivers being probed (oxidation vs thermally driven dehydration/side reactions vs polymorphic/crystallisation changes) and different boundary conditions (maximum temperature, temperature ramp, dwell time/time-above-melt, atmosphere and sealing, sample mass/surface area, and cooling rate). Therefore, improved comparability requires standardised tests and reporting, including at minimum: (1) atmosphere composition (air vs inert; purge/flow rate; sealing quality), (2) thermal history descriptors (degree of superheat, dwell times, ramp rates, and cumulative time above melting), (3) sample geometry/mass and container material/headspace, and (4) DSC method details (heating/cooling rate, baseline method, replicate strategy). Studies that report both cycling and molten holding performance under controlled atmospheres are particularly valuable because they help disentangle which ageing drivers dominate for a given PCM and application duty cycle.

Chemical reaction with environmental factors, such as oxygen, water vapour, and metals within heat exchangers, is another factor that can significantly impact PCM stability. For instance, molten nitrate salts, under the typical operating temperature of 560 °C and oxygen partial pressure of 0.2 atm, decompose to produce a nitrite content of 4.5 mol% [110]. Elevated temperatures can lead to further decomposition reactions, primarily involving the breakdown of nitrite ions into oxide ions (e.g., O^{2-}) and various gaseous species, including nitrous gases (NO , NO_2), nitrogen (N_2), and oxygen (O_2) [111]. These kinds of decomposition reactions are particularly concerning because of the release of toxic nitrous gases [112] and the formation of oxide ions that can exacerbate the corrosion of the structural material [113,114]. The eutectic mixture of molten chloride salts, $MgCl_2/KCl/NaCl$, is known to exhibit strong hydrophilic behaviour when exposed to atmospheric moisture. This interaction leads to the formation of oxide and hydroxide impurities upon heating, which in turn initiates the corrosion of the container materials [115]. This salt mixture exhibits similar behaviour with 316 stainless steel (at 700 °C), when the latter is used as the structural material of TES. This causes the dissolution of Cr, Ni, and Fe species into the molten salt. This dissolution is attributed to the hydrolysis of $MgCl_2$, which generates MgO and gaseous HCl . The HCl gas permeates the environment around and reacts with the inner surface of 316 stainless steel to produce metal chlorides ($CrCl_2$, $NiCl$, and $FeCl_2$). These chlorides subsequently integrate into the molten salt, altering its composition and negatively impacting its chemical compatibility and performance [116].

The separation of components in mixtures or the occurrence of incongruent melting presents another considerable challenge, as different constituents in a PCM blend may melt and solidify at varying rates. This phenomenon can lead to phase separation, altering the phase change temperatures and diminishing the PCM blend's effective heat storage capacity. For instance, sodium acetate trihydrate exhibits incongruent melting, where instead of forming a uniform melt of the trihydrate, phase segregation occurs, resulting in the precipitation of anhydrous sodium acetate from the solution [117]. To mitigate this issue, strategies such as incorporating low concentrations of polymer additives have been employed to suppress phase segregation in these systems [118]. The aforementioned factors are listed in Fig. 9.

Despite extensive investigation of degradation mechanisms, few studies explicitly define quantitative thresholds for acceptable PCM ageing in practical TES systems. From a system performance perspective, reductions in latent heat capacity exceeding 10–15% are generally considered detrimental, as they directly reduce storage density, system efficiency, and economic viability [98,119,120]. Similarly, shifts in phase transition temperature greater than $\pm 2-3$ °C may significantly impair heat exchange efficiency and system control, particularly in applications with narrow operating temperature windows, such as building thermal management and electronic cooling.

Mass loss due to volatilisation or decomposition should ideally

Table 11

Comparative summary of major phase change materials across thermal energy storage applications. Note: The values presented in this table represent approximate ranges intended for general comparison. The precise thermophysical properties of individual PCMs are provided in the corresponding detailed tables elsewhere in this paper. In certain cases – particularly for eutectic mixtures – the principal characteristics, such as melting temperature and phase change enthalpy, may vary significantly depending on composition and formulation.

PCM category	Typical materials	Melting temperature (°C)	Latent heat (kJ/kg)	Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	Thermal stability	Corrosion risk	Relative cost	Typical applications
Organic: paraffins	n-Hexadecane, n-octadecane, n-eicosane, n-docosane	5–60	140–250	0.2–0.4	Excellent	Very low	Medium	Building thermal regulation, solar TES, HVAC
Organic: non paraffins: fatty acids	Lauric, palmitic, stearic acid	20–70	150–250	0.2–0.3	Very good	Low–moderate	High	Buildings, solar water heating, electronics cooling
Organics: non paraffins: esters & alcohols	Methyl palmitate, PEG, octadecanol	10–70	120–210	0.2–0.5	Good	Very low	Medium–high	Passive cooling, textiles, building envelopes
Inorganic: salt hydrates	CaCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O, Na ₂ SO ₄ ·10H ₂ O	20–120	150–280	0.5–1.5	Moderate	High	Low	Building heating, domestic hot water, solar TES
Molten salts	Sodium nitrate, potassium carbonate	150–900	100–250	0.5–1.5	High	Very high	Low–medium	Concentrated solar power, industrial waste heat recovery
Inorganic: metallic PCMs	Gallium, aluminium alloys	30–300	25–100	15–70	Excellent	Moderate–high	High	High-power electronics cooling, aerospace
Eutectic mixtures	Fatty acid blends, salt eutectics	10–120	120–180	0.4–1.5	Good	Moderate	Medium–high	Buildings, refrigeration, solar thermal

Fig. 9. Factors leading to PCM degradation.

remain below 5% over the expected service lifetime, as higher losses can lead to substantial changes in thermophysical properties and may also introduce safety concerns, including vapour pressure buildup and leakage [100,101]. For high-temperature PCMs, acceptable corrosion rates for metallic containment materials are typically below 0.02–0.09 mm/year, ensuring structural integrity and long operational lifetimes exceeding 20 years [121–123]. Corrosion rates exceeding these limits substantially increase maintenance requirements and system downtime, undermining the economic and environmental advantages of TES deployment.

Furthermore, acceptable degradation thresholds must be evaluated within the broader system context, accounting for thermal cycling frequency, application-specific performance tolerances, safety margins, and lifecycle cost constraints. In practical engineering design, conservative thresholds are often adopted to ensure reliability, particularly for large-scale TES installations where component replacement is costly and operational disruption is highly undesirable. Establishing such quantitative benchmarks, therefore, plays a critical role in guiding PCM selection, material compatibility assessment, and long-term system optimisation.

In summary, the ageing of PCMs results in significant deterioration across multiple properties, including appearance, thermal stability, and chemical composition. These changes reduce the material's energy storage efficiency, reliability, and lifespan. To ensure the suitability of PCMs for long-term TES applications, comprehensive testing, including accelerated thermal cycling and chemical analysis, is essential. Strategies to mitigate ageing effects, such as enhancing PCM formulations and controlling environmental interactions, are crucial for improving their durability and performance [103,124–129]. Table 12, taken from

Table 12

Thermal cycling effect on different PCMs, taken from reference [98]. The original references are also cited here.

Cycle count	PCM	Observed effects	Original Ref.
50 cycles	Dodecanoic acid/RDP	Minor change in melting enthalpy (~4%) with minor influence on phase transition temperature	[130]
100 cycles	Paraffin/expanded graphite	Reduction in melting enthalpy by 3% and a slight decrease in melting temperature (<1 °C)	[119]
200 cycles	Paraffin	Fusion heat and melting point dropped by 25.2% and 33.72%, respectively	[131]
5000 cycles	Polymeric-paraffin	Melting enthalpy reduced by 2.9% with minimal impact on phase transition temperature	[132]
8500 cycles	Paraffin/graphite	Reduction in energy storage capacity by 10.5%	[133]
10,000 cycles	Paraffin (XBL-22)	Fusion heat reduced by 9.1%	[120]

reference [98], summarises the impact of thermal cyclic tests for some of the PCMs.

3.2. System-level implications of PCM degradation in TES applications

Whilst material degradation mechanisms are often investigated at laboratory scale, their consequences at the system level are equally critical for the reliable operation of TES installations. PCM ageing can significantly influence system performance, thermal efficiency, operational stability, and maintenance requirements. Reductions in latent heat capacity directly decrease storage density, necessitating larger storage volumes or more frequent charging–discharging cycles to deliver the same thermal output, thereby increasing system complexity and operational cost.

Changes in melting temperature and thermal conductivity affect heat exchanger design and control strategies. Even modest temperature shifts can impair heat transfer efficiency, particularly in applications with narrow temperature margins, such as building thermal regulation,

district heating networks, and electronic cooling systems. Furthermore, degradation-induced reductions in thermal conductivity can exacerbate thermal resistance, increasing charging and discharging times and reducing overall system responsiveness.

Corrosion and material compatibility issues represent major system-level challenges, as they directly impact container integrity, heat exchanger lifespan, and system safety. Elevated corrosion rates can lead to leakage, contamination of working fluids, and premature component failure, thereby increasing maintenance frequency and operational downtime. In large-scale TES systems, these effects can significantly compromise economic feasibility and system reliability.

From an operational perspective, PCM degradation also affects system control and monitoring requirements. Ageing-induced property changes necessitate adaptive control strategies and periodic recalibration of thermal management systems to maintain stable performance. In addition, safety considerations become increasingly critical for high-temperature PCMs, where degradation products may pose risks related to toxicity, flammability, or pressure buildup.

Consequently, system-level design must account for anticipated PCM ageing by incorporating conservative material selection criteria, robust containment strategies, corrosion-resistant materials, and modular designs that facilitate inspection and replacement. Integrating material degradation behaviour into holistic TES system optimisation is therefore essential to ensure long-term reliability, safety, and economic viability.

3.3. Ageing tests in PCMs

The above insights underscore the importance of conducting thorough ageing tests to evaluate the performance of PCMs before their deployment in TES applications. The following sub-sections outline the procedures and measurement techniques employed to evaluate the stability of PCMs.

3.3.1. Evaluation of PCM stability

To understand and mitigate PCM ageing, a variety of ageing test procedures are employed. One common approach is thermal cycling – repeatedly subjecting the PCM to alternating high and low temperatures to simulate prolonged use [71,134]. PCMs are cycled between temperatures where they fully crystallise at the lower limit and fully melt at the upper limit. This cycling is often conducted under either normal atmospheric conditions or controlled inert atmospheres, such as argon, dry air, or nitrogen, to observe the effects of oxidation [101,102]. Another approach involves maintaining the PCM at a constant high temperature for an extended period, allowing the observation of changes in stability under persistent thermal stress [135–137].

3.3.2. Techniques for PCM ageing monitoring

Measurements taken during ageing tests include visual inspection for changes in colour, viscosity, and homogeneity, all of which serve as qualitative indicators of degradation [138]. Mass loss measurements using techniques like thermogravimetric analysis can help quantify material degradation over time, providing insights into the volatility and stability of the PCM [101]. Techniques like high-resolution mass spectrometry, ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy, and Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy can help in understanding the chemical decomposition of the PCMs over time [101,139,140]. Gas chromatography (GC-MS) can be employed to identify the presence of degradation products [125]. Additionally, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) can provide critical insights into the latent heat of a PCM and the melting point, which reflect the energy storage capacity and the temperature range of the material. These parameters are essential for assessing the PCM's suitability for specific thermal management applications [125,139,141].

It should be noted that, despite the extensive body of literature on PCM ageing, reported ageing results frequently exhibit significant inconsistencies. Rather than representing fundamental contradictions,

these disparities largely reflect variations in experimental design, material characteristics, and operational parameters. By synthesising findings across multiple studies, several consistent performance trends emerge.

First, thermal stability is strongly governed by the interplay between operating temperature and atmospheric exposure. PCMs subjected to prolonged high-temperature cycling in oxidative environments consistently exhibit accelerated degradation, whereas those tested under inert atmospheres demonstrate substantially enhanced stability. Second, encapsulation strategies play a critical role in mitigating degradation by reducing oxidative contact, suppressing volatilisation, and limiting container-PCM interactions. Microencapsulation and polymer-based containment have repeatedly been shown to improve long-term cycling performance, although at the expense of reduced effective thermal conductivity.

Third, material purity and formulation complexity critically influence ageing behaviour. High-purity paraffins and eutectic fatty acid mixtures exhibit superior cycling stability compared to commercial-grade materials containing trace impurities that catalyse degradation pathways. In salt hydrate systems, the incorporation of nucleating agents and thickening additives effectively suppresses phase separation and supercooling, thereby enhancing long-term thermal reliability.

Finally, inconsistencies in reported degradation rates often originate from non-standardised testing methodologies. Differences in heating rates, cycle duration, temperature ramp profiles, and failure criteria substantially influence measured performance metrics. Harmonisation of experimental protocols would therefore greatly improve data comparability and facilitate the development of robust predictive lifetime models.

3.4. Innovative enhancement strategies: nano-enhanced and encapsulated PCM

In recent years, significant research efforts have been directed toward overcoming the intrinsic limitations of conventional PCMs, particularly their low thermal conductivity, phase segregation, supercooling, and long-term stability issues. Several innovative strategies have been proposed, including: (a) integration of heat pipes and extended surfaces (e.g., fins [142]); (b) dispersion of highly conductive additives [143]; (c) microencapsulation [144]; and (d) nanoencapsulation [145]. These approaches aim to enhance heat transfer rates, improve thermal reliability, and extend operational lifetimes.

Among these strategies, the dispersion of nanoparticles has emerged as one of the most promising and versatile solutions. Nano-enhanced PCMs (NePCMs), produced by incorporating high-conductivity nanoparticles and metallic nanoparticles into base PCMs, demonstrate markedly improved thermal conductivity, accelerated melting–solidification kinetics, and reduced supercooling [146]. In addition, several studies report modest reductions in melting temperature, which can be advantageous for low-temperature thermal management applications, including building energy storage and electronics cooling [147]. Despite these benefits, nanoparticle loading introduces important trade-offs. Excessive nanoparticle concentrations may reduce latent heat capacity, increase viscosity, promote particle agglomeration, and degrade long-term cycling stability [148].

Microencapsulation and nanoencapsulation techniques offer complementary advantages by providing physical containment of PCMs within polymeric, inorganic, or hybrid shells [145,146,148]. These strategies effectively suppress leakage, improve chemical stability, and reduce interactions with container materials, whilst enabling easier handling and integration into composite systems. Nanoencapsulation, in particular, offers superior surface-area-to-volume ratios, leading to faster heat transfer and enhanced cycling durability [149]. However, encapsulation layers introduce additional thermal resistance and may increase material cost, necessitating careful optimisation [148].

Overall, nano-enhanced and encapsulated PCMs represent highly

promising pathways toward next-generation TES materials. Continued advances in nanomaterial synthesis, surface engineering, and scalable fabrication techniques are expected to further improve performance, reliability, and economic feasibility, thereby accelerating the deployment of advanced PCM-based TES technologies across building, industrial, and renewable energy applications.

4. Compatibility of structural materials (metals and alloys + encapsulating materials) with PCMs

PCMs are often corrosive to a vessel material. Generally, organic PCMs pose minimal corrosion risk, except for a few cases [150,151]. However, most inorganic PCMs are highly corrosive [152]. The compatibility between structural materials and the PCM is crucial for ensuring the long operational life of a TES system [152]. The favourable properties of metals, such as material resistance, heat conductivity, durability, resistance to abrasion, malleability, and ductility, make them the best candidates for PCM storage [153]. The interaction between the PCM and the storage material plays a significant role, especially the corrosion aspect, as this corrosiveness can degrade both the performance and longevity of the TES container [154], but management systems as well [155]. Corrosion leads to thinning and weakening of materials, making them brittle and prone to collapse. Ensuring a long service life for the TES system is paramount because the system's life cycle significantly impacts the overall environmental benefits of renewable energy [156]. Among PCMs, as mentioned, organic ones typically exhibit the least corrosion when in contact with heat exchanger materials. In contrast, alternatives like salt hydrates can cause corrosion of metal components, such as containers and heat exchangers [157]. Studies on molten nitrate salts and other high-temperature PCMs have revealed that prolonged exposure to elevated temperatures can lead to degradation, as seen in molten salt systems where nitrate salts decompose into nitrites, increasing their corrosive nature [158]. Metals like stainless steel 316 L, when subjected to thermal cycling in molten salts, showed changes in composition due to the dissolution of chromium and nickel oxides [159].

4.1. Corrosion process

Corrosion is a complex chemical and electrochemical phenomenon that leads to the deterioration of materials, particularly metals and their alloys, due to interactions with their environment. At its core, the process involves redox reactions where the metal acts as the anode, losing electrons, whilst a reduction reaction occurs at the cathodic site. Key parameters influencing this process include temperature, pH, oxygen availability, humidity, and the presence of aggressive ions such as

chlorides [160,161]. These factors can either accelerate or inhibit corrosion depending on the material and environmental conditions. For instance, an increase in temperature typically enhances the rate of corrosion due to higher reaction kinetics, whereas pH variations can shift the balance between corrosion and passivation [162,163]. The thermodynamic and kinetic aspects of corrosion, including activation energy and Gibbs free energy, play crucial roles in determining whether a material is susceptible to corrosion under given conditions [164].

4.2. Impacts of corrosion

Corrosion is a critical concern for materials, particularly when interacting with PCMs in TES applications [165]. These materials can exacerbate localised forms of corrosion, such as pitting, as presented in Fig. 10. Pitting corrosion, characterised by the formation of small but deep cavities, arises when protective oxide layers on metals break down, often under the influence of aggressive ions like chlorides present in some PCMs. Once this localised damage is initiated, these pits can propagate rapidly, undermining the structural integrity of the material and leading to failure. Generally, the corrosion of a PCM can be a combination of various corrosion types, a fact that increases the complexity of the problem [155]. Some other types of corrosion that could arise in TESs are crevice, Stress Corrosion Cracking, Hydrogen Damage, Corrosion Fatigue, intergranular, uniform, galvanic, selective leaching, erosion, and fretting corrosion [166]. The detailed description of corrosion types is out of the scope of this review. Different forms of corrosion can also be seen in Fig. 11.

Furthermore, the cyclic thermal behaviour inherent to PCMs can aggravate corrosion mechanisms. Repeated heating and cooling cycles can induce thermal stresses and cause microstructural changes in the material, potentially accelerating crack formation. These cracks, especially when coupled with environmental stressors or high-pressure conditions, can lead to leaks, ruptures, or even catastrophic failures in critical systems like heat exchangers, storage vessels, and pipelines [165]. In addition, corrosion by-products such as oxides, hydroxides, or salts often form on metal surfaces. Whilst these products might temporarily slow further corrosion by forming passive layers, they can also foster localised attack by creating differential aeration cells [167,168]. The dynamic interaction between PCMs and corroding surfaces magnifies these effects, requiring stringent material selection and protective measures. Ultimately, the presence of PCMs and their associated corrosive potential significantly shortens the operational lifespan of metallic components, increasing the demand for proactive maintenance, advanced corrosion-resistant materials, and effective inhibition strategies to mitigate these detrimental effects.

Fig. 10. Pitting corrosion of steel in the presence of water and air.

Fig. 11. Different forms of corrosion [155].

4.3. Corrosion tests

4.3.1. Procedures

To evaluate the susceptibility of materials to corrosion, various tests are performed under controlled laboratory conditions. One standard approach involves immersing material samples in the liquid phase of PCMs contained within airtight bottles [121,160]. These samples are maintained at a constant temperature for a specified period to assess corrosion under static conditions. Another procedure employs thermal cycling, where material samples are alternately heated and cooled whilst immersed in the PCM [169]. This approach simulates real-world applications where PCMs experience phase transitions and temperature fluctuations. Both static and thermal cycling tests help identify the roles of temperature, phase change, and exposure duration on material degradation.

Stress corrosion testing may also be considered, where mechanical stresses are applied to the material while it is exposed to corrosive environments. Techniques such as U-bend tests or slow strain rate tests are commonly used to study the synergistic effects of mechanical stress and corrosion on material performance [170,171].

4.3.2. Measurements

Several metrics and methods are used to quantify and analyse corrosion. The most common method involves measuring the mass loss of a material sample after exposure to the corrosive medium following ASTM standards [172,173]. This data is used to calculate the corrosion rate, often expressed in millimetres per year (mm/year), using the formula given in Eq. (5).

$$\text{Corrosion Rate (mm/year)} = \frac{(K \times W)}{(A \times T \times D)} \quad (5)$$

where K is a constant, W is the mass loss (in g), A is the surface area (in cm^2), T is the exposure time (in h), and D is the material density (in g/cm^3).

Visualisation techniques such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM) are employed to examine surface morphology and identify localised features like pitting or cracks [174]. Microscopy provides detailed insights into the mechanisms of corrosion and the material's failure modes. Energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) can help in understanding the chemical composition of the corrosion products [175]. Additionally, monitoring the pH of the PCM or the surrounding environment is critical. Changes in pH can indicate the progression of corrosion and the release of ions into the medium [176]. For example, a decrease in pH might signal the production of acidic by-products, which can further accelerate the corrosion process.

4.4. Known corrosion compatibility with metals and alloys

Salt hydrates, though prone to corrosion, are particularly suitable for

heat storage due to their high latent heat of fusion, good thermal conductivity, and low cost. To mitigate corrosion, PCMs are often encapsulated, and various metal containers have been tested for their thermal conductivity and mechanical resistance. The long-term compatibility of metals with PCMs depends on minimising undesirable interactions, typically evaluated through the corrosion rate. Studies have shown that aluminium is the most compatible container material for many PCMs, demonstrating low mass loss and minimal surface deterioration after long exposure.

For instance, Calabrese et al. [123] found that aluminium alloys showed good corrosion stability with magnesium nitrate hexahydrate, whilst carbon steel and copper alloys displayed significant corrosion after only a few hours. Moreno et al. [122] tested various metals like copper, aluminium, stainless steel, and carbon steel with different PCMs and concluded that stainless steel and aluminium are generally the most compatible materials for use with many PCMs, although the choice of material depends on the specific PCM application.

Some studies, such as Marín et al. [177], revealed that stainless steel is the most resistant to corrosion across a range of PCMs, with minimal mass loss and low corrosion rates. Aluminium also showed good performance with organic PCMs, but was prone to corrosion when used with certain inorganic PCMs. Copper, commonly used for its high thermal conductivity, showed corrosion in contact with certain PCMs, although protective coatings can mitigate this issue.

Various studies, including those by Cabeza et al. [178], have investigated the compatibility of metals like aluminium, brass, copper, steel, and stainless steel with different PCMs. Stainless steel consistently showed good compatibility with salt hydrates across a range of temperatures, making it a preferred material for PCM storage containers. However, other metals, like aluminium and copper, were found to be suitable under specific conditions depending on the PCM and operating temperature.

Nagano et al. [179] and Ushak et al. [177] similarly observed that stainless steel (SUS316) and aluminium performed well in corrosion tests with salt hydrates and magnesium nitrate hexahydrate. In contrast, severe corrosion was noted at the salt-air interface for other metals. Additionally, Dindi et al. [180] demonstrated that a boron nitride coating effectively prevented corrosion on stainless steel when exposed to molten aluminium-silicon alloy, remaining stable over 720 cycles of melting and solidification.

Paul et al. [121] explored materials suitable for use in adipic acid-based PCM storage systems, identifying stainless steel (316 L) as a strong candidate due to its performance in short-term corrosion tests. However, while 316 L stainless steel exhibits excellent corrosion resistance, its higher cost compared to carbon steel presents a challenge for cost-effective system design. Therefore, the balance between material performance and economic considerations must be carefully evaluated when selecting materials for PCM systems. Table 13, taken from [155], summarises the suitability of different PCM materials with encapsulant

Table 13

Summary of the suitability of different PCM materials with the encapsulant material, taken from [155].

Heat storage container	Recommended type of PCM	Not recommended type of PCM	Recommended with caution
Stainless steel	Capric acid, 75% Capric: 25% palmitic acid, 45% Capric: 55% lauric acid, SP22 (fatty acid/paraffin wax), Micronal® (paraffin), RT-21, RT-25, SP-21E (inorganic), HS- 24P	Paraffin wax, sodium acetate trihydrate, lauric acid, myristic acid, palmitic acid, stearic acid	ZnCl ₂ ·3H ₂ O, Zn (NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O, K ₂ PO ₄ ·7H ₂ O, NaOH·1.5H ₂ O, K ₂ HPO ₄ ·6H ₂ O, MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O, Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ ·5H ₂ O, SrBr ₂ ·6H ₂ O, CaCl ₂ , Na ₂ S, CaO, MgSO ₄ , Ca(OH) ₂ , MgCl ₂ , Al–34%Mg–6%Zn alloy, phenylacetic acid, glutaric acid, 59.5% Na ₂ CO ₃ –40.5% NaCl Inorganic salt SP21E, CaCl ₂ , Na ₂ S, NaCl–KCl–ZnCl ₂
Stainless steel 304	Ester PureTemp 23, SP21E (inorganic salt), fatty acid eutectics, stearic, palmitic, myristic, lauric acids		
Carbon steel	Ester PureTemp 23, fatty acid eutectics		
Stainless steel 316	Ester PureTemp 23, SP21E (inorganic salt), fatty acid eutectics		Na ₂ HPO ₄ ·12H ₂ O, Na ₂ SO ₄ ·10H ₂ O, Na ₂ S·9H ₂ O, Na ₂ S·5H ₂ O
Fe-Cr-Al alloy	Molten nitrate	Molten chlorine salt	Molten carbonates
Mild steel	Mg(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O–Ca (NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O (1:1), MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	SrBr ₂ ·6H ₂ O, MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O, Zn (NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O, SP25	Acetamide
Copper	Ester PureTemp 23, SP21E (inorganic salt), paraffin wax, sodium acetate trihydrate, RT-21, RT-25, SP22, Micronal®, ZnCl ₂ ·3H ₂ O, MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	Phenyl acetic acid, glutaric acid	Stearic, palmitic, myristic, lauric acids, Na ₂ S·nH ₂ O
Aluminium	Stearic, palmitic, myristic, lauric acids, SrBr ₂ ·6H ₂ O, MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O, Ester PureTemp 23, fatty acid eutectics, paraffin wax, sodium acetate trihydrate, RT-21, RT-25, Micronal®, acetamide, Linpar 17/1820 (paraffin)		Capric acid blends, Na ₂ HPO ₄ ·12H ₂ O, Na ₂ SO ₄ ·10H ₂ O, HS- 24P, CaCl ₂ , MgSO ₄ , MgCl ₂ , Ca(OH) ₂ , SP21E (inorganic), SP22, phenyl acetic acid, glutaric acid
Perspex	Capric acid blends, SP22, Micronal®		
Brass	SP22, Micronal®	Capric acid blends, Micronal®	Fatty acids
Copper alloys (Cu 101, Cu 110)	1-Octadecanol		
Magnesium alloy (AZ91D)	1-Octadecanol	Fatty acids	
Ni C7521	Hexadecanoic acid, octadecanoic acid, 1-octadecanol		
Aluminium alloys (ENAW 2024, 3003,	Na ₂ SO ₄ ·10H ₂ O		

Table 13 (continued)

Heat storage container	Recommended type of PCM	Not recommended type of PCM	Recommended with caution
6063, 1050)			
St37 steel	SrBr ₂ ·6H ₂ O		
IACW (inertised asbestos)	Nitrates		
Stainless steel 310, 347	34.42 wt% NaCl–65.58 wt% LiCl		
Inconel 625 (>58% Ni)	34.42 wt% NaCl–65.58 wt% LiCl		
PVC	SP22, SP25		59.5% Na ₂ CO ₃ –40.5% NaCl, 68.05% Na ₂ SO ₄ –31.95% NaCl

material.

Corrosion processes in phase change material-based thermal storage systems are intrinsically complicated. This is due to the following reasons: the broad diversity of PCM compositions, the wide variety of structural materials that come into contact with these PCMs, and the range of operating conditions upon which the systems operate. These reasons can significantly impact system performance and durability. Scientists have documented anti-corrosion/mitigation of corrosion strategies of PCM with improved corrosion protection. There are numerous methods for defending against corrosion in metals, e.g., including corrosion inhibitors, applying packaging techniques on PCMs, and applying coating coverings. Acidic environments are addressed specifically by corrosion inhibitors – for instance, proline and methionine may retard the corrosion rate of metals in acidic environments.

PCMs may also be encapsulated as a viable alternative. This method, besides minimising corrosion risk and thermal conductivity, also avoids direct contact of the PCM with the container to ensure protection of the materials [155]. Another commonly employed and cost-effective technique is the deposition of an inert coating over the metal surface, forming a corrosion protection barrier. Finally, the chemical composition of the metal itself also determines its ability to resist corrosion. In Fe/Cr/Si alloys, for example, the content of silicon is quite significant – a 1.5% silicon alloy is most resistant when contacted with molten aluminium [155].

4.5. Compatibility of PCMs with encapsulation materials

As discussed in Section 3.4, encapsulation has emerged as an effective strategy to improve the structural stability, handling, and functional performance of PCMs, whilst mitigating leakage issues that may arise from direct contact between the PCM and its container. Nevertheless, the long-term reliability of TES systems based on encapsulated PCMs critically depends on the chemical and physical compatibility between the PCM and the encapsulating material [181].

A wide range of materials have been proposed for encapsulation, including metallic alloys (e.g., aluminium, copper, stainless steel, nickel [182–187]), ceramics (e.g., silicon dioxide, alumina, calcium carbonate [188]), and polymers (e.g., polystyrene (PS), high- and low-density polyethylene (HDPE, LDPE), polypropylene (PP), polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and polycarbonate (PC) [189,190]).

Whilst numerous studies have examined corrosion phenomena in metals in contact with PCMs, as presented in the previous sections, and comparatively few investigations have addressed ceramic–PCM compatibility, polymer–PCM interactions have been more extensively studied using experimental approaches. These typically include (i) immersion of polymer samples in molten PCMs with monitoring of mass

Table 14
Review of polymer-PCM compatibility studies.

Study	Materials tested	PCMs tested	Results
Lázaro et al. [191]	HDPE, LDPE, PET, PP	4 organics 1 inorganic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LDPE bottles had the highest mass variation and big deformations. When RT20, RT25, and RT26 were used, the recommended plastic encapsulation material was PET. When TH24 was used as the molten salt, and water sorption was not desired, PEHD was chosen. PP, PET, and PELD showed a big mass increase.
Castellón et al. [192]	HDPE, LDPE, PP	3 organics 1 inorganic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> LDPE and PP showed the worst behaviour (mass variation and deformation during mechanical tests) compared to HDPE for encapsulating organic PCMs.
Oró et al. [193]	Polypropylene (PP), high-density polyethylene (HDPE), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and polystyrene (PS)	9 inorganics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PP, PS, PET, and HDPE did not show changes in weight or physical appearance of the samples. In addition, they had no formation of precipitates, pitting processes or bubbles. This means that they were not affected by a process of degradation and are compatible with the PCMs studied
Browne et al. [194]	Perspex	5 organics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perspex was recommended for all tested PCMs.
Ostrý et al. [195]	Polypropylene (PP-H), high-density polyethylene (PE-HD), and polyvinylchloride (PVC-U)	2 organics 2 inorganics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The organic PCMs had a greater ability to penetrate the PE-HD and PP-H compared with the inorganic PCMs. Mass changes in PE-HD and PP-H samples did not exceed 6.9% when immersed in organic PCMs and 1.8% in inorganic PCMs. PVC-U samples exhibited almost negligible (less than 0.1%) mass variation in all cases.
Bantová et al. [196]	Polycarbonate (PC), polypropylene (PP-H), polyethylene (PE 500), and polyethylene terephthalate (PET)	3 organics 1 inorganic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inorganic PCM (Rubitherm SP24E) and organic bio-based coconut oil exhibited good compatibility with all plastics. Organic PCMs (Parafol 17-97, Rubitherm RT24) showed significant penetration of the PP-H and PE 500 (weight changes up to 5.80%).

variation and visual changes, and (ii) mechanical characterisation of specimens after thermal exposure. The main studies and their outcomes are presented in Table 14.

The reported results indicate that compatibility strongly depends on both PCM chemistry and polymer type. In conclusion, encapsulation material selection must rely on systematic compatibility testing – including long-term immersion, thermal cycling, mechanical assessment, and diffusion analysis – in addition to thermal performance and economic considerations, to ensure durable, safe, and scalable PCM-based thermal energy storage systems.

5. Challenges and considerations for large-scale deployment of PCM-based TES systems

5.1. Scalability, commercialisation, and long-term reliability challenges

Despite the substantial progress in PCM development and laboratory-scale demonstrations, several challenges remain that hinder large-scale deployment and commercialisation of PCM-based TES systems. Among these, scalability of material synthesis, manufacturing cost, system integration complexity, and long-term reliability represent the most critical barriers [197].

From a scalability perspective, many high-performance PCMs and enhancement strategies rely on complex synthesis routes, costly raw materials, or energy-intensive fabrication processes. For example, nano-enhanced and encapsulated PCMs often involve multi-step processing, surfactant usage, and precise particle dispersion control, which significantly increase production cost and complicate mass manufacturing [198]. Scaling these technologies to industrial volumes whilst maintaining material uniformity, quality control, and performance reproducibility remains a major challenge.

Commercialisation is further constrained by economic considerations, including raw material availability, system-level cost, and lifecycle economic performance [199]. Whilst paraffin-based and salt hydrate PCMs benefit from relatively low material costs, advanced composite and nano-enhanced formulations often exhibit higher upfront investment requirements. Cost competitiveness with established thermal storage technologies, such as sensible heat storage and thermochemical storage, therefore, remains a critical benchmark. In this context, lifecycle cost analysis, durability, and maintenance

requirements become decisive factors for industrial adoption [199,200].

Long-term reliability represents one of the most significant challenges for real-world deployment. Many PCMs exhibit gradual degradation of thermophysical properties under prolonged thermal cycling, including latent heat reduction, melting point drift, phase segregation, and container corrosion, as detailed above. These ageing phenomena directly impact system efficiency, operational stability, and maintenance frequency. In large-scale TES installations, component replacement or system downtime can lead to substantial economic losses, underscoring the need for robust material selection, advanced containment strategies, and predictive lifetime assessment models.

In addition, regulatory and safety considerations play an increasingly important role in commercial deployment [199]. Flammability, toxicity, pressure buildup, and leakage risks associated with certain organic and inorganic PCMs necessitate strict compliance with building codes, industrial safety standards, and environmental regulations. These requirements impose additional constraints on material formulation, encapsulation design, and system integration.

Addressing these challenges requires a multidisciplinary approach integrating material science, manufacturing engineering, system optimisation, economic assessment, and regulatory compliance. Continued advances in scalable synthesis methods, low-cost nanomaterial production, modular system design, and real-time condition monitoring are expected to significantly improve the commercial feasibility and long-term reliability of PCM-based TES technologies.

5.2. Sustainability, environmental impact, and end-of-life considerations

Sustainability and environmental considerations are increasingly important in the evaluation and deployment of PCM-based TES systems. Whilst PCMs offer significant potential for energy efficiency improvement and carbon emission reduction, their environmental footprint, toxicity, and recyclability must be carefully assessed to ensure sustainable lifecycle performance.

Organic PCMs, such as paraffins and fatty acids, generally exhibit low acute toxicity and favourable environmental compatibility. However, their derivation from petroleum-based or agricultural feedstocks raises concerns regarding fossil resource dependence, land use, and indirect greenhouse gas emissions. In contrast, bio-based PCMs derived from renewable resources offer improved sustainability profiles but

often face challenges related to cost, scalability, and long-term stability.

Inorganic PCMs, particularly salt hydrates and molten salts, present mixed environmental characteristics. Whilst they are often abundant and cost-effective, certain formulations may contain toxic or corrosive constituents, such as nitrates, chlorides, or heavy metal salts, posing risks related to environmental contamination, occupational exposure, and disposal. Metallic PCMs, although highly efficient thermally, raise concerns regarding resource scarcity, recyclability, and potential ecological impact associated with metal extraction and processing.

Encapsulation strategies, polymeric shells, and nano-enhancement additives further complicate end-of-life management due to material heterogeneity, potential nanoparticle release, and recycling challenges. The environmental implications of nanoparticle synthesis, dispersion stability, and post-use recovery remain insufficiently understood, highlighting the need for comprehensive life-cycle assessments.

Future research should prioritise the development of environmentally benign PCMs, recyclable encapsulation materials, and scalable recycling pathways, alongside robust environmental impact assessments. Integrating sustainability metrics into material selection and system design will be essential for ensuring that PCM-based TES technologies deliver not only technical and economic benefits but also long-term environmental value.

6. Summary and future outlook

This review provides an analysis of latent heat storage (LHS) systems and phase change materials (PCMs) utilised in thermal energy storage (TES). It explains the mechanisms by which PCMs absorb heat during solid-liquid phase transitions, emphasising the importance of melting temperatures and other critical properties – thermal, physical, kinetic, and economic – when selecting suitable PCMs. The review also highlights the advantages of eutectic mixtures, which offer consistent phase transitions but are often less commonly used due to their lower heat capacities. It also stresses the significance of PCM stability over repeated charge/discharge cycles, as thermal ageing can significantly degrade performance. Moreover, the time that a PCM spends at an elevated temperature is another critical parameter that should be taken into account. The study of cycling and of prolonged exposure of a PCM at high temperature will provide new insights into TES systems. Corrosion and materials compatibility between PCMs and storage materials is discussed, with findings indicating that stainless steel is often preferred for its compatibility with various PCMs, particularly salt hydrates, but is not used so often due to increased costs. Given these challenges, it is essential to conduct tailored preliminary tests designed for the specific materials and operational conditions of the suggested PCM system, focusing on corrosion issues. These tests will provide critical insights into the compatibility and longevity of the components, ensuring safe and efficient scaling up to industrial applications.

As TES systems become increasingly important for integrating renewable energy into the grid and reducing dependence on fossil fuels, a key challenge is to ensure the durability and efficiency of the materials used in these systems. Increasing interest has been centred on nano-enhanced PCMs, encapsulation, and hybrid TES systems, consisting of viable and effective approaches. Future research should focus on developing and validating high-thermal-conductivity materials for internal heat transfer tubes in PCM-based storage systems, with particular emphasis on long-term performance under harsh operating conditions, including mechanical stress, corrosion exposure, and repeated thermal cycling. Additionally, exploring novel alloys and composites that combine the strengths of metals such as aluminium, stainless steel, and copper could yield cost-effective materials with optimised thermal and corrosion properties. Continued investigation into PCM-material interactions, especially with newer PCM formulations and under extreme operating conditions, will also be vital to understand the thermal stability of both organic and inorganic PCMs. Addressing the impact of environmental factors such as impurities, moisture, and air exposure on

corrosion rates will further improve material selection and TES performance. Lastly, the combination of non-corrosiveness, cost-effectiveness and scalability must be considered, especially in large-scale energy storage projects. The efforts should be directed at lowering the costs of corrosion-resistant materials like stainless steel, reducing the corrosion rate of PCM, i.e. by the addition of amino acids containing heavy halogen atoms or extending the life of lower-cost alternatives to support widespread TES adoption. Additionally, the review also highlights the challenges and considerations associated with the large-scale deployment of the TES system. Therefore, to further advance the development and large-scale deployment of PCM-based TES technologies, several critical research gaps and challenges must be systematically addressed:

(i) Standardisation of testing methodologies:

There is a lack of unified protocols for thermal cycling, ageing assessment, and material compatibility evaluation. The development of standardised testing frameworks is essential to improve data reproducibility, facilitate cross-study comparisons, and enable reliable lifetime prediction.

(ii) Long-term durability and degradation modelling:

Although numerous short-term studies exist, long-duration experimental investigations and predictive degradation models remain limited. Future work should focus on establishing mechanistic ageing models and accelerated lifetime testing approaches that realistically represent long-term operational conditions.

(iii) Optimisation of advanced PCMs:

Although nano-enhanced PCMs (NePCMs) and advanced encapsulated PCMs demonstrate promising improvements in thermal conductivity and overall thermal performance, significant challenges remain, including nanoparticle agglomeration, dispersion instability, latent heat reduction, synthesis complexity, scalability, and cost. Future research should therefore prioritise the optimisation of nanoparticle type, concentration, surface functionalisation, and encapsulation strategies to enhance thermal conductivity, cycling stability, and system safety whilst minimising latent heat penalties. Achieving a balanced trade-off between performance enhancement, durability, manufacturing simplicity, and economic feasibility will be essential for large-scale deployment.

(iv) System-level integration and optimisation:

Improved understanding of heat exchanger design, thermal management strategies, dynamic control, and multi-physics system modelling is required to bridge the gap between material-scale performance and full-scale TES system operation.

(v) Scalability and commercialisation barriers:

High material costs, complex fabrication processes, and limited industrial-scale manufacturing capabilities hinder large-scale deployment. Advances in scalable synthesis routes, modular system design, and cost-effective fabrication methods are necessary to accelerate market penetration.

(vi) Sustainability and environmental impact:

Comprehensive life-cycle assessments, recyclability studies, and environmentally benign material development remain underexplored. Integrating sustainability metrics into PCM selection and TES system design is essential to ensure long-term environmental and societal benefits.

(vii) Field validation and long-term monitoring:

Large-scale demonstration projects and extended operational monitoring are required to validate laboratory findings, identify unforeseen degradation mechanisms, and refine system reliability models. Addressing these interconnected challenges will be crucial for enabling the widespread adoption, commercial viability, and long-term sustainability of PCM-based thermal energy storage technologies.

(viii) Hybrid TES system development:

Hybrid TES systems that integrate latent, sensible, and thermochemical storage mechanisms represent a highly promising direction for maximising energy density, operational flexibility, and system efficiency. Combining PCMs with high-conductivity matrices, thermochemical materials, or cascaded storage configurations can exploit the complementary advantages of different storage mechanisms. Systematic experimental validation, coupled with multi-physics modelling and techno-economic analysis, will be essential to accelerate the development and real-world deployment of such hybrid TES architectures.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Deepak Sharma: Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Adamantini Loukodimou:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Bénédicte Champel:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Shiladitya Paul:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The data is available in the manuscript.

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